

CAREER INFORMATION GUIDANCE STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING STUDENTS' CHOICE OF VOCATIONAL AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION SUBJECTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DELTA STATE

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Career Guidance, Strategies, Students' Choice, Vocational and Technical Education

Abstract: *The study was conducted to identify the Career information guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. One specific purposes, research questions and hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised of 3,585 (1,594 males and 1991 females) teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects from 488 public secondary schools in the 11 Education Zones in Delta State. Sample size of 717 teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 10 items entitled: Career Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students' Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (CGSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.97. Seven hundred and seventeen copies of the questionnaire were administered with the help of five research assistants, and 542 were retrieved from the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions, and t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that career information guidance strategies included: providing students with information related to job opportunities in the vocational and technical education industry; educating students on the skills required for certain jobs in vocational and technical education; keeping students updated on current trends in the job market in relation to VTE jobs and educating students on how to prepare for job search e.g. teaching students how to write CV. The hypothesis tested showed that gender teachers of vocational and technical education subjects did not show significant differences in their mean responses on career information guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary*

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schools in Delta State. The implication of the findings is that lack of career guidance in secondary schools may perpetuate students' low interest and enrollment in VTE subjects, leading to a shortage of skilled workers in various industries which may exacerbate the skills gap in various industries, making it challenging for employers to find qualified candidates. It was recommended that National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) should map-out specialized mandatory career guidance subjects for secondary schools. Through this policy framework students can be properly guided towards enrolling for vocational subjects.

Introduction

Education is a significant tool for promoting learning and the development of skills and knowledge that lead to self-sufficiency and better living standards. Education is also a systematic process of training and instruction meant to impart knowledge, acquire skills, potentials and abilities that enable an individual to meaningfully contribute to the growth and development of his society and nation. In Nigeria, education is the cornerstone that promotes national and economic progress. It is the foundation for achieving sustainable development (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). Education is defined as the development of various potentials, including intellectual, psychological, moral, physical, aesthetic, cognitive, and active potentials. Both socialization and development of institutional education in schools play significant roles in the process of acquiring knowledge and skills. As a product, education can be defined as a result of processes and services (Adesemewo and Sotonade, 2022). The product achieved by the school is called an “educational product” and

consists of key components that contribute decisively to the quality of education provided by the organization (Adesemewo and Sotonade, 2022). The most important component include the educational product provided by the teachers and the educational services comprise the delivery of knowledge and skills that leads to educational development. Education plays a significant role in preparing students for vocational and technical education (VTE) by providing them with foundational knowledge, skills and competencies that are essential for success in VTE programme after graduations. Education helps students with solid foundation in subjects like mathematics, science, and language, which are crucial for VTE programmes. It also exposes students to various career options, enabling them to make informed decisions about their future careers. Vocational and technical education programme is one of the academic programmes in tertiary institutions.

Vocational education is defined as any type of education whose primary goal is to train and prepare people for work in recognized

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vocations. It follows that vocational education is a broader word than technical education, which is defined as a post-secondary vocational training program with the primary goal of producing technicians (Ojimba, 2012). Vocational and Technical Education (VTE), according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), is a broad term that refers to aspects of the educational process that include, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, as well as the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Vocational and Technical Education is any form of education that strives to improve students' abilities and potential so they can do tasks or work in a certain vocation effectively (Okoro in Ozoemena, 2013). VTE can be delivered in a variety of ways: It may be formal or informal, structured or unstructured and it may be institutionalized or community-based. The main goal of vocational and technical education subjects is to prepare students for the workforce. VTE, according to Winer in Igbozurike, Peter and Usman (2018), strives to broaden the learner's skills, talents, knowledge, and awareness of work etiquette and attitude needed to thrive in a specific line of work or occupation. According to this definition, TVE can also be described as a type of education that fosters the development of learners' technical and vocational skills, expertise, dexterity, talents, and attitudes through any combination

of formal or informal education, on-the-job training, or off-the-job training.

Vocational and technical education provides students with a structured programme of learning experiences that includes career exploration, basic academic and life skills support, achievement of high academic standards, leadership development, industry-specific job preparation, and advanced and continuing education. Okoye and Okwelle (2013) viewed VTE as an education system expected to produce a competent workforce that can compete and excel in a rapidly changing environment and improve a country's economy. Vocational and technical education is concerned with the development of skills, competences, and knowledge for the working world (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization International Centre for TVET (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2019). It includes formal, informal, and non-formal education. It influences people's attitudes and develops abilities and knowledge from fundamental to advanced levels. The importance of VTE cannot be overstated, particularly in the light of the fact that many secondary school dropouts and even university graduates often lack essential occupational and life skills (Eze and Okorafor, 2012). According to Igbozuruike, Ebonu and Onu (2017), continued neglect of VTE is the cause of this situation. Although it has become abundantly evident that lack of practical skills among school dropouts is the primary cause of Nigeria's growing unemployment rate. It is

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stated that less than one percent of secondary education in Nigeria is designed to promote VTE and skills development (Igbozuruike, 2018). As there is scarcely any discernible leadership or direction for revitalizing VTE, the terrible situation has not improved and is really becoming worse.

There is an urgent need for Nigeria's focus to be towards self-sufficient and sustainable means of subsistence that VTE provides. However, it appears that secondary schools in Nigeria have failed to guide students to make effective career choices that would improve their capacity for self-employment amidst the current economic downturn being faced in Nigeria. The perception of Vocational and Technical education (VTE) in Nigeria is influenced by societal attitudes and educators perspectives. As Okoye and Arimonu (2016) suggest, there is a prevailing notion in Nigerian society that VTE subjects are suitable for academically weak students who may not pursue higher education. This perception is compounded by the fact that teachers responsible for delivering VTE programme often lack adequate knowledge about the relevance and importance of these subjects. (Adewale, Aderonmu, Fulani, Babalola and Awoyera, 2018). This appears to result in poor students' interest in VTE subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. It is therefore pertinent that career guidance strategies are adopted so as to improve students' interest in VTE.

Career guidance refers to services designed to help people of all ages and stages of life make educational, training, and employment decisions and manage their careers (Partha, 2020). Career guidance assists students in reflecting on their goals, interests, credentials, and talents. It assists students in comprehending the labor market and educational institutions and connecting this to what they know about themselves. Career guidance attempts to teach people how to plan for and make decisions about their education and employment. Walter (2012) stated that career guidance improves access to information about the labor market and educational prospects by organizing, systematizing, and making it available when and where individuals need it. Partha (2020) stated that the goals of career guidance are that it provides quality life planning education and proper career services which are classified with our developmental needs of different stages of growth; it supports the creation of good career decisions according to their abilities, experiences and orientations among others. It empowers students to make reasonable career choices and set career goals which help them build meaningful life. The International Youth Foundation in Nwachi and Ndimele (2021) stated that career guidance and career planning exercises would impact these youth in two major ways: (a) to help them understand their interests and aptitude and thereby choose appropriate career opportunities and (b) to link them with appropriate skills

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training to join a skilled workforce and access better livelihood opportunities. It may also help those youths who have dropped out in returning to school and continuing their education. For career guidance to be successful in attracting students there is need for the development of strategies.

A strategy is a plan that is created to attain a certain goal. Amesi, Akpomi, and Okwuanaso (2014) defined strategy as the purposeful selection of several activities to produce a distinct blend of value. Strategy is a systematic approach to managing a given situation through re-positioning of activities and functions. Ofoyuru and Too-Okema in Nwachi and Ndimele, (2021) defined strategy as the art of devising or implementing thoughtful plans or techniques toward a goal. Thus, career guidance strategies are the systematic approaches utilized by secondary schools for attracting students to study VTE subjects.

Career guidance is a set of activities that prepares people of any age at a specific point in their lives to identify their own abilities, competencies, and interests and to make decisions that affect their education, employment, and other areas where they might gain and apply abilities and competencies. This definition was provided by the Council of European Union in 2004. On the other hand, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in Ilu and Adomeh (2020) defined career guidance as a collection of services and initiatives set up to help people

of any age at any stage of their lives make decisions about their education, training, and careers and manage those decisions. According to Watts and Fretwell in Don and Nguyen (2015), the purpose of career guidance is to enable people of all ages and stages of life to make decisions about their education, training, and occupations as well as to manage their careers. Career guidance consist of three primary components: career education, career counseling and career information (Watts and Fretwell in Don and Nguyen, 2015).

Career education is a structured programme designed to equip individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for career planning and decision-making. It encompasses a broad curriculum that integrates academic learning with career development activities to prepare students for the world of work (Don and Nguyen, 2015). Career education helps individuals explore various career options, understand job market trends, and develop employability skills such as communication, problem-solving, and teamwork. It also fosters self-awareness by enabling individuals to identify their interests, strengths, and values in relation to career choices (Loan and Van, 2015). Schools, vocational institutions, and universities incorporate career education into their curricula to ensure that students make informed career decisions. Ultimately, career education aims to enhance lifelong learning and adaptability to the changing demands of the labour market.

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Career counseling is a professional service that assists individuals in making informed career choices based on their interests, abilities, and values. It involves one-on-one or group sessions where trained career counselors provide guidance, assessment, and resources to help individuals explore suitable career paths. Career counseling helps individuals understand their career goals, identify potential challenges, and develop strategies for overcoming obstacles in their career journey. Counselors use various tools, such as aptitude tests, personality assessments, and labour market information, to support clients in making well-informed career decisions. This service is beneficial for students, job seekers, and professionals who want to change careers or advance in their current roles. Career counseling ultimately aims to enhance career satisfaction and personal fulfillment by aligning individuals' aspirations with realistic career opportunities.

Similarly, career information which offers details on courses, vocations, and professional trajectories, is often the emphasis of career guidance in schools. Information on the job market is also included. Schools, universities, colleges, training facilities, public employment/workplaces, the voluntary/community sector and the commercial sector were listed by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in Ilu and Adomeh (2020) as areas where such services may be provided. Career guidance might be conducted

on an individual or group basis, face-to-face or virtually (via help lines and/or websites). The resources at the counselors' disposal include career educational programmes, employment search initiatives, and counseling interviews. The idea of career guidance and counseling extend beyond the initial decisions about a person's education and profession and covers job leisure, mental health, and the balancing of a person's professional and private duties (Prelovsky, 2017). Loan and Van (2015) asserted that career advice and orientation services are services meant to assist people of any age and at any stage in their lives, allowing them to choose their educational path, vocation and career management.

Given that the current notion of career guidance activity is to assist students in making decisions based on their interests, passions, and talents while taking into consideration present and future prospects, the implications of these criteria for career guidance services are clear (Loan and Van, 2015). It suggests that the psychological makeup of the teenager must be taken into account in light of the dynamic character of the workplace. According to Ilu and Adomeh (2020), career guidance services provided by secondary schools include: provision of individual and small counseling services to in-school adolescents in order to help them adjust to their social, personal, academic and vocational needs; consultations with parents regarding special concerns and needs of students in a collaborative manner so

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that the parents can be well informed about their wards' academic progress and interactions with the school personnel where teachers and school administrators are consulted for counseling needs for the students. In other for administrators of vocational and technical education to ensure that students get interested in VTE subjects it is expected to apply certain career guidance strategies.

Career guidance strategies refer to the approaches, methods, and techniques used to support individuals in making informed decisions about their career paths. These strategies aim to help individuals explore their interests, skills, and values; identify career options; and develop plans to achieve their career goals (Partha, 2020). Career guidance strategies are essential in the secondary school system for addressing students' physical, social, emotional, vocational, and academic issues in order to improve their wellness, academic performance, and career choice making. This may have prompted Eremie and Jackson (2019) to argue that every teacher should be guidance focused in the process of carrying out his or her duties with the goal of creating an influence in the lives of the students. Partha (2020) asserted that career guidance strategy is a plan for moving our lives in the right direction. Nwachi and Ndimele (2021) stated that the career guidance strategies available in schools and communities in general include information services, testing services, placement services, appraisal services, orientation services,

evaluation services, referral services, research services, follow-up services, consultation, coordination, collaboration, instruction, and institutional support. Partha (2020) opined that academic information, career information, group guidance, counseling, orientation, and assessment are part of the career guidance strategies.

Career information is a catch-all term for all career-related information (Xiao, 2017). Career information that is complete comprises practice resource information, career news information, career policy information, career assessment information, and so on (Cai, 2020). Cai categorized career information services that provide information to students as career information relating to the labor market, information on laid-off and unemployed personnel, information on rural surplus labor market and on-the-job personnel professional information. The acquisition and use of professional information creates a link between people, businesses, and society. Cai (2020) further stated that career information updates students with information related to a particular career choice thereby fostering career progress. Professional information has a positive impact on an individual's life in several ways. It helps people understand the requirements of society for various professional roles, cultivates awareness of those roles, comprehends corporate culture, values, experience, and norms, establishes professional ethics, improves social adaptability of individuals, and is helpful

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in socializing people. Hanson, et al (2017) noted that in addition to career information, career expos are important guidance strategy for Increasing students' choice of VTE subjects.

The concept of gender refers to the culturally established economic, social, and political duties, responsibilities, rights, entitlements, and obligations that come with being female or male, as well as power dynamics between genders. Sex which is a term associated with gender is defined as the categorization of individuals as male, female or intersex. These include chromosomes, (e.g., XX, XY), hormone level and reproductive anatomy. According to Godfredtson in Mayange and Umar, adolescence students have an understanding of the sex type and prestige level of common careers, for instance, female students might avoid choosing careers that are generally perceived as low social prestige. Similarly, a study conducted by Nwachi and Ndimele (2021) revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the influence of career guidance strategies on students' career choice in secondary schools. These opinions of scholars are however, based on reasoning, models or speculated career guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State; rather than on direct observations or measurement. It is against this backdrop that the researcher conducted the study to empirically identify the career guidance

strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

Vocational and Technical Education programme provides practical and theoretical instruction to the recipients who might need employment in commerce and industry or in any type of enterprise which utilizes tools and machinery. It is believed that the acquisition of practical skills relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life could lead to self-sustainability or self-reliance. Sadly, students in secondary schools appear to have a negative attitude towards VTE subjects in their schools. Experience in supervision and students' job orientation shows that students dislike works or employment tasks that will put them to handling equipment and machinery either in the laboratory or in the work field. Some students aspire to get white collar jobs and feel embarrassed about jobs which are related to practical work or work in factories. With this experience, most students aspiring to make career choices lack the needed information for career choice. Thus, the task of choosing a career is made more challenging for students who do not have a clear direction or aim with relation to their career talent. Some young adults who are about graduating from secondary schools have increased anxiety on career choice. Most of the students lack the ability to accurately assess their own interests, talents, skills, strengths, and deficiencies.

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Despite the introduction of entrepreneurship studies in the secondary education curriculum, students have continued to struggle in making career choices that would make them gainfully employed. Another issue of grave concern is that of unemployment, which has become one of the most frustrating scenarios in the society. It is undeniable that the problem of unemployment exists because of skill gap which may be attributed to inadequate career guidance, limited exposure to VTE opportunities, and other challenges related to a variety of factors in selecting a profession. It is on this note that the researcher is worried about the career guidance strategies that could bridge this gap, empowering students to explore viable career paths and make informed subjects choice of vocational and technical education subjects in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to identify the career guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to identify:

- 1 the career information guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the career information guidance strategies for increasing students'

choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on career information strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study was conducted in Delta State, located in the South-South region of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 3,585 (1,594 males and 1991 females) teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects from 488 public secondary schools in the 11 Education Zones in Delta State. Sample size of 717 teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 50 items entitled: Career information Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students' Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (CGSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.97. Seven hundred and seventeen copies of the questionnaire were

administered with the help of five research assistants, and 542 were retrieved from the respondents. Data collected were analysed using mean to answer the research questions, and t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the p-value was less than or equal to the 0.05 level of significance. The decision is to accept when P-value is greater than 0.05 and reject when the P-value is less than or equal to 0.05

Results

The results are presented in the order of the five research questions and five null hypotheses in the tables below:

Research Question One: What are the career information guidance strategies for increasing students’ choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State?

The data providing answers to the above research question are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Career Information Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students’ Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools

S/N	Items on Career Information Guidance Strategies	N	Mean	Std.	Remarks
1.	Providing students with information on job opportunities in the vocational and technical education programme	542	2.97	.94	S
2.	Educating students on the skills required for certain jobs in vocational and technical education	542	3.14	.84	S

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3.	Keeping students updated on current trends in the job market in relation to VTE jobs	542	3.24	.76	S
4	Informing students on the opportunities available in the vocational and technical job market	542	3.33	.66	S
5	Educating students on how to prepare for job search e.g. teaching students how to write CV	542	3.28	.62	S
6.	Taking students on excursions to different industries to learn first-hand from employers of labour on job skills required for employment	542	3.39	.61	S
7.	Creating Alumni networks where former vocational and technical education graduates can share their career experiences	542	3.31	.65	S
8.	Organizing workshops and seminars on vocational and technical education career exploration	542	3.38	.63	S
9.	Offering one-on-one career guidance sessions with qualified counselors who can provide personalized advice based on students' interests	542	3.32	.63	S
10.	Offering one-on-one career guidance sessions with qualified counselors who can provide personalized advice based on students' skills	542	3.32	.60	S

Note: S= Strategies

Table 1 shows that all the strategies have mean scores ranging from 2.94 to 3.40. This implies that the career information guidance strategies include: providing students with information related to job opportunities in the vocational and technical education industry; educating students on the skills required for certain jobs in vocational and technical education; keeping students updated on current trends in the job market in relation to VTE jobs; educating students on how to prepare for job search e.g. teaching students how to write CV; taking

students on excursions to different industries to learn first-hand from employers of labour on job skills required for employment and so on.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on career information strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

The t-test analysis of data collected to test the null hypothesis one is presented in Table 2

Table 2: t-test Analysis on the Career Information Strategies for Increasing Students’ Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary schools based on Gender

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std.	Df	Alpha	t-cal	P-Value	Decision
1	Male	254	2.98	.89	540	0.05	.256	.030	Significant
	Female	288	2.96	.98					
2	Male	254	3.18	.80	540	0.05	1.048	.255	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.10	.87					
3	Male	254	3.26	.76	540	0.05	.432	.920	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.23	.77					
4	Male	254	3.26	.63	540	0.05	.900	.932	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.31	.61					
5	Male	254	3.36	.62	540	0.05	.939	.746	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.41	.59					
6	Male	254	3.28	.66	540	0.05	1.073	.487	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.34	.65					
7	Male	254	3.41	.62	540	0.05	.787	.939	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.36	.63					
8	Male	254	3.30	.63	540	0.05	-.463	.519	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.33	.64					
9	Male	254	3.34	.62	540	0.05	.631	.117	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.30	.58					
10	Male	254	3.36	.68	540	0.05	1.06	.210	Not Significant
	Female	288	3.30	.64					

The result of the t-test analyses in Table 2 indicates that nine out of the ten identify strategies have their P- values ranging from .210 to .939 which are greater than 0.05 indicating that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers of vocational and technical education subjects. While strategy, providing students with information on job opportunities in the vocational and technical education programme only has P-value of .030 which is less than 0.05 indicating a significant difference between male and female teachers of

vocational and technical education subjects. This indicates that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on career information strategies for increasing students’ choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State is not rejected.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that the respondents indicated that the career information guidance strategies included:

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providing students with information related to job opportunities in the vocational and technical education industry; educating students on the skills required for certain jobs in vocational and technical education; keeping students updated on current trends in the job market in relation to VTE jobs and educating students on how to prepare for job search e.g. teaching students how to write CV. Others are: taking students on excursions to different industries to learn first-hand from employers of labour on job skills required for employment; creating Alumni networks where former vocational and technical education graduates can share their career experiences; organizing workshops and seminars on vocational and technical education career exploration; offering one-on-one career guidance sessions with qualified counselors who can provide personalized advice based on students' interests and offering one-on-one career guidance sessions with qualified counselors who can provide personalized advice based on students' skills. The researcher is of the view that the result may be because, with the advancement in technology, especially global communication and the internet, the role of career information in the career guidance process has become increasingly crucial. The collection and utilization of career information serve as a bridge connecting individuals, businesses and societies. It has a significant impact on individuals, work environments and overall growth through career guidance. Personal access to professional information

offers individuals the necessary support to understand the specific requirements of different professions within the society.

The findings of this study are consistent with the view of Cai (2020) who stated that career information updates students with information related to a particular career choice thereby fostering career progress. Professional information has a positive impact on an individual's life in several ways. It helps people understand the requirements of society for various professional roles, cultivates awareness of those roles, comprehends corporate culture, values, experience, and norms, establishes professional ethics, improves social adaptability of individuals, and is helpful in socializing people. The findings are in consonance with Isa (2013) who reported that career information helps cultivate awareness of professional roles, facilitates an understanding of corporate culture, values, experiences, and norms, and enables individuals to determine their professional aspirations. Moreover, it enhances personal social adaptability, supports individual social integration, and fosters the development of a sound professional perspective. By leveraging this information and the guidance provided by career professionals, individuals are better equipped to make wise career choices. Additionally, it positively contributes to the physical and mental well-being, as well as the personal growth and development of workers in various fields. The findings are consistent with the study of Okirigwe, (2020) who noted that

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secondary school students can access career information from various sources to explore different professions and make informed decisions about their future. This finding is in line with the statement of Do and Nguyen, (2015) who states that, by segmenting career information based on different categories, individuals can access tailored resources and guidance specific to their circumstances and goals. This comprehensive approach to career information ensures that individuals have access to the necessary information and support to make informed decisions and navigate their career paths effectively. The findings of the study are in agreement with Okirigwe, (2020) who noted that it may also include information about universities, colleges, vocational institutions, and certification programmes, as well as insights into the educational and training needs for various careers. The outcome of the study also supports the opinion of Hanson, et al (2017) who noted that in addition to career information, career expos are important guidance strategy for increasing students' choice of VTE subjects. It was also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on all the career information guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State; except strategy number one in Table 3. The findings are also supported by Zalevski and Swischowski (2019) who opined that the underrepresentation of women

in science, engineering, and technology fields is worrisome as it leads to inequality of opportunities and contributes to persistent skill shortages and the gender pay gap. Barry, Bacon, and Child in Simon, Alberto and Shay (2011) who stated that the significance of specific career contexts, such as the characteristics of a profession or the types of careers individuals pursue, particularly in relation to culture is often overlooked. The findings are in line with Boudreaux and Nikolaev (2019) who found that gender perspective is prominent in research on work-family dynamics and careers; there is an ongoing call for more detailed analyses of the various aspects of gender effects. The findings contradict Owodunmi, Igwe, Sanni and Onatunde, (2016) who noted that boys are consistently found to perform better than girls on vocational and technical education achievement tests. This suggests that boys are more inclined towards vocational and technical education subjects compared to girls. The findings are in consonance with Echeonwu and Abali (2022) who opined that to overcome gender inequality in vocational and technical education, more attention should be given to gender mainstreaming by making concerns and experiences of both men and women an integral part of the design, implementation and evaluation of these programmes.

Conclusion

The study identified the career guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in

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secondary schools in Delta State. The findings of the study revealed that career guidance strategies, such as career information, career fair, career orientation activities, mentorship programmes and computer-assisted career guidance can play a crucial role in shaping students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools. The study also concluded that gender, location, school levels (Junior/senior), years of experiences of teachers of vocational and technical education subjects did not differ in their mean ratings on career information guidance strategies, career fair guidance strategies, career orientation guidance strategies, mentorship career guidance strategies and computer-assisted career guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

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choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) should map-out specialized mandatory career guidance subjects for secondary schools. Through this policy framework students can be properly guided towards enrolling for vocational subjects. This will reduce unemployment, poverty and other social vices associated with them.
2. Federal and State government should develop more policies to support the integration of career guidance in secondary schools, including funding for career guidance programmes in secondary schools.

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